

Nonperforming Assets and its Impact on Financial Performance: A Study on Banking Sector in India

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Abstract

Non-Performing Assets is one of the key indicators of banking sector to measure the efficiency of performance of banks. A high level of NPAs leads to large number of credit defaults which affect the profitability and wealth of banking companies. This paper describes the consistency level in profit and NPA of public sector banks, private sector banks and foreign banks. The objectives of this study is to find out the trend of NPA and Profit of public, Private & Foreign sector banks and to measure the relationship between NPA and profitability of public, private and foreign sector banks. This study is based on secondary data those are collected from Reserve Bank of India website. This paper finds that in Private sector banks increase in NPA leads to decrease in profit and in foreign banks NPA has less significant effect on profitability.

Keywords: Non performing asset, portfolio, wealth, Public Sector Bank, Private Sector Bank, Foreign Bank

INTRODUCTION

The banking industry in India has been witnessing a series of revolutionary changes and noteworthy transformation since 1991 after introduction of LPG policy and new economic and financial sector reforms. The process of Liberalization aimed to free banks from too much of regulations. The focus was on self-regulation. Self-regulation requires prudential norms to be laid down. On the eve of economic reforms in 1991, it was recognized that the banks were burdened with huge amount of Non-Performing assets (NPAs), which were not revealed in the balance sheets. The banks had gone very weak. Balance sheets were hiding more than what they revealed. After the first nationalization of Banks in 1969, certain tendencies emerged in the banks that led to the emergence of NPAs.

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The concept of NPAs emerged as a contemporary issue when Reserve Bank of India (RBI) introduced the prudential norms on the recommendations of the Narsimham committee in the year 1992-93. The prudential norms as laid down by RBI states that “An asset is considered as Non Performing if interest or installment of principal due remains unpaid for more than 90 days”. In simple words as long as the expected income is realized from the assets, it is treated as performing asset but when it fails to generate income or deliver value on due date, it is treated as non-performing asset”. With a view to moving towards International best practices and to ensure greater transparency, the “90 Days overdue” norm for identification of NPAs had been adopted from the year ending 31st march, 2004.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Kiran and Jones (2016) made a study on effects of NPA on the profitability of banks. The objective of this study is to examine the relationship between NPA and profitability of banks. They have used secondary data and applied correlation & regression in their study. The study concludes that large banks are able to adjust the losses on account of NPAs but small banks are not able to afford it and public sector banks are facing more issues due to NPAs.

Singh (2016) conducted study on Non-performing assets of commercial banks and its recovery in India. The paper highlights the status of Non-performing assets of Indian scheduled commercial banks in India. This study is secondary in nature and the time period 2000 to 2014 is used for the study. This paper finds that ineffective recovery, willful defaults and defective lending process are the important factors for the rise of NPAs in banks and NPAs are responsible for reducing the earning capacity of banks.

Rao & Patel (2015) studied Non-performing assets management of public sector banks, private sector banks and foreign banks in India. This paper considers the aggregate data of public sector, private sector and foreign banks and interprets the NPA management from the year 2009 to 2013. The study uses Least square method for estimating gross NPAs and ANOVA test to find out the significant difference between gross NPA ratio to gross advances ratio. This study finds that gross NPA to gross advance is increasing for public banks, ratio of gross NPA to gross advances for public sector, private sector and foreign banks does not have significant difference between 2009 to 2013.

Narula & Singla (2014) evaluate the non - performing assets of “Punjab National Bank and its impact on profitability & to see the relation between total advances, Net Profits, Gross & Net NPA”. The study uses the annual reports of Punjab National Bank for the period of six years from 2006-07 to 2011-12. These papers conclude that

there is a positive relation between Net Profits and NPA of PNB. It is because of the mismanagement on the part of bank.

Arora and Ostwal (2014) conducted a research on “Unearthing the Epidemic of Non-Performing Assets: A Study of Public and Private Sector Banks” which deals with the concept of Non-performing assets and analyze the classification of loan assets of public and private sector banks. It also explores the comparison of loan assets of Public sector and private sector banks. The study concluded that private sectors are improving due to decline in NPAs ratio as compared to Public sector banks. There is need to check the NPAs of public sector banks so that Indian banking system can be made efficient.

Srinivas K T (2013) made an effort to identify the “Non-performing assets at Commercial banks in India.” This paper highlights the various general reasons which convert advances/ assets into NPA and also give suitable suggestion on findings to overcome the mentioned problem.

Olekar and Talawar (2012) studied “NPA management with reference to Karnataka central co-operative bank ltd.”, where they described conceptual data about NPA and on the other hand, they calculated few NPA related ratios and used trend projection method to predict next year advances for the bank. Their finding includes the considerable reduction of NPA for the bank and some suggestions for recovery of NPA.

Kaur and Saddy (2011) in the research paper entitled “A Comparative Study of Non-Performing Assets of Public and Private Sector Banks” an attempt is made to clarify the concept of NPA, the factors contributing to NPAs, the magnitude of NPAs, reasons for high NPAs and their impact on Indian banking operations. Besides capital to risk weight age assets ratio of Public and Private sector banks, management of credit risk and measures to control the threat of NPAs are also discussed.

Malyadri and Sirisha (2011) this study examine the NPA of Public Sector banks and Private sector banks of weaker sections for the period seven years in India. The secondary data compiled from Report on Trends and Progress of Banking in India, 2004-10 which has been analyzed by statistical tool such as percentages and compound Annual Growth rate. This study reveals that the public sector banks have achieved a greater penetration compared to the private sector banks.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The definition of banking is the acceptance of deposits and lending of loan. Whereas they pay interest at different rates on the deposits they accept from the customers and

they collect interest on the advances they lend to the customers. They keep a certain margin between the interest charged and interest paid. The margin should be in such a way that the banks can afford to pay all expenses in conducting the banking activities. The balance amount after payment of all expenses and charges will be the profit for the banks and the profit is shared between the shareholders. In case, the banks are not able to recover the amount lent to their borrowers, the level of profits comes down. All loan accounts are classified as performing assets or non-performing assets. In classifying the non-performing assets, the availability of security or net worth of the borrower/guarantor is not considered for such classification.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study are:

- To study the trend of NPA and operational performance of public, private and foreign sector banks.
- To measure the relationship between NPA and profitability of public, private and foreign sector banks.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sources of data- This study is based on secondary data collected from the website of Reserve Bank of India and other authentic sources.

Sample Design- Banks are categorized into public sector banks, Private Sector banks and foreign sector banks. In our study we have considered all the banks to establish relationship between NPA and Profit.

Study period- This study has covered 5 years from 2011 to 2015.

Statistical tools- The Statistical Techniques used for analysis are simple regression & Coefficient of Correlation to analyze the relationship between dependent variables and independent variable. Descriptive statistics are also used for studying variations on sample banks profitability and NPA.

Variables-Independent and Dependent variables of the selected sample banks for the study are:

1. **Dependent variables**

Profit

2. **Independent variables**

NPA-Non Performing Asset.

Hypothesis

- H^1_0 = NPA does not influence profitability in Public sector banks.
- H^2_0 = NPA does not affect profitability in Private sector banks.
- H^3_0 = NPA does not effect profitability in Foreign sector banks.

DATA ANALYSIS

Table No 1

CV Analysis

	PUBLIC SECTOR BANKS		PRIVATE SECTOR BANKS		FOREIGN BANKS	
	PROFIT (%)	NPA (%)	PROFIT (%)	NPA (%)	PROFIT (%)	NPA (%)
Average	10.24	2.99	11.55	1.38	8.24	3.42
S.D	0.78693092	0.840272083	1.152405652	1.053301355	1.946781572	5.33
C.V	0.076848723	0.28127134	0.099775381	0.762880148	0.236152497	1.56

Source: Self Compiled

Public sector banks make consistent profit over a sample period from 2011-2015 which is evident from C.V of profits of public sector banks i.e. 0.0768. So far as NPA of public sector banks is concerned there is a variation of NPA to the extent of 0.28 as compared to private sector banks i.e. 0.76 and that of foreign banks 1.56, so it signifies that there is significant inconsistency in NPA among private and foreign banks. Private and foreign banks adopt their own approaches to deal with NPA problems where-as public banks follow specified guidelines in dealing with NPA. There is more or less consistency in level of making profit by private and public sector banks as compared to that of foreign banks where consistency level is less.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN NPA AND PROFIT

$$Y_e = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NPA + \varepsilon$$

Where,

Y_e = PROFIT

β_0 = Constant or the intercept value of Y

β_1 = Slope of the independent variables

NPA = Non Performing Asset

ε = Error Term

Table No 2: Regression statistics Public Sector Banks

Source: Self Compiled

From the regression statistics as given above it is found that there is a positive relationship between Profit and NPA in public sector banks i.e. 0.009 which is very small. It means if profit increases then NPA also increases, it does not mean increase in NPA leads to increase in profit. There are other factor which contributes towards increase in the profit of public sector banks. Here P value is 0.636 which is above standard 0.05 i.e. $P > 0.05$. So, null hypothesis H_0 is accepted. It signifies that there is less significant relationship between NPA and profitability of public sector banks. The relationship is positive however the impact is very insignificant. NPA does not influence much the profitability of Public Sector Banks. But it should not be allowed to go unchecked.

Table No 3: ANOVA Table - Public Sector Banks

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	9.978460699	0.577840192	17.26855	2.09E-15
NPA	0.089146361	0.186453329	0.478116	0.636722

Source: Self Compiled

$$\text{Profit} = 9.97 + 0.08\text{NPA} + \mu\epsilon$$

Here β_0 is the estimated constant of the regression and the value of β_0 is 9.97. Here NPA shows positive contribution towards Profit. The NPA coefficient (β_1) is 0.08, it means 1 unit change in NPA leads to 0.08 unit change in Profit.

Multiple R	0.095189
R Square	0.009061
Adjusted R Square	-0.03058
P Value	0.636722

Table No 4: Regression statistics Private Sector Banks

Multiple R	0.642434
R Square	0.412721
Adjusted R Square	0.381812
P Value	0.001687

Source: Self Compiled

The relationship between Profit and NPA in private sector banks is 0.41. It means change in one unit of NPA leads to 41% change in Profit. Here null hypothesis H_0^2 is rejected because the significance value is 0.001 i.e. $P < 0.05$. It concludes there is a significant positive relationship between NPA and profit. If NPA is increasing and Profit also increasing it means profit is backed by other sources. Had NPA been less profit would have been more.

Table No 5: ANOVA Table – Private Sector Banks

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	12.52051	0.331099	37.81498	2.39E-19
NPA	-0.70288	0.192353	-3.65412	0.001687

Source: Self Compiled

$$\text{Profit} = 12.57 - 0.70\text{NPA} + \mu e$$

The constant intercept is 12.52. In the above table NPA contributes negatively towards profit. The NPA coefficient (β_1) is shown as -0.70. Thus, it means 1 unit increase in NPA leads to -0.70 decrease in profit. It means that when NPA will increase then profit will decrease.

Table No 6: Regression statistics Foreign Banks

Multiple R	0.183947
R Square	0.033837
Adjusted R Square	0.006232
P Value	0.275785

Source: Self Compiled

Looking up the regression table we can find that the relationship is positive between NPA and profit in foreign banks i.e. 0.033. The number is very negligible. Here p value is 0.275 i.e. $P > 0.05$. It implies that the null hypothesis H_0^3 is accepted that there is less significant relationship between profit and NPA. The impact of NPA on profit is very insignificant irrespective of positive relationship between them.

Table No 7: ANOVA Table – Foreign Sector Banks

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	7.793321	0.362002	21.52838	9E-22
NPA	0.063866	0.057686	1.107138	0.275785

Source: Self Compiled

$$\text{Profit} = 7.79 + 0.06\text{NPA} + \mu\epsilon$$

In the above table constant intercept is 7.79 and the NPA coefficient (β_1) is 0.06. It reveals 0.06 change in profit if NPA changes in 1 unit. In foreign sector banks NPA contributes positively towards profit.

FINDINGS

Mostly every country's economic growth is influenced by its financial system. The financial system mainly comprises banking sector. Indian banking system of late has been facing the NPAs problem which is the main concern for the bottom line of the banking sectors.

The study shows that in public sector banks NPA and Profit are positively related. It does not mean that NPA increases profit. In public sector banks profit continuously increases in spite of increase in NPA. This is due to other sources of earning revenue, if NPA is controlled the profit would rise more proportionately than before.

Our study also reveals that there is a negative relationship between NPA and profit in Private sector banks. NPA causes decrease in profit of private sector banks. The measure source earning income in private sector banks is mostly from interest of loans and advances unlike public sector banks. Therefore private sector banks are more cautious and vigilant in recovering the loans and advances from their customer which the public sector banks do not follow.

So far as foreign sector banks are concerned NPA and profitability are independent to each other though they have a positive relationship as indicated from our study.

SUGGESTIONS

The study suggests the following mechanisms to curb the volume of NPAs taking place in Indian Banking sector:

1. Sufficient Manpower:

Banks need adequate manpower for effective NPA management. There is a misconception that NPA management is nothing but recovery of banks dues.

However this is not correct. Effective NPA management involves analysis of non-performing assets, planning, deciding strategy for recovery, selecting accounts for immediate action follow up, interaction with the borrowers, dealing with compromise/write off proposals etc. It needs involvement and understanding of staffs' continuously, so that there will be a focused attention on recovery. In order to control the level of NPAs it is necessary for bank officials to:

- Identify the borrower properly.
- Scrutinize the proposal carefully.
- Give adequate & timely finance.
- Ensure utilization.
- Monitor and follow up closely.
- Rephrase or reschedule the account for reasons beyond the control of the borrower.

2. Awareness & Training Camps for Borrowers:

Borrower's awareness level regarding non-performing assets is very less. Banks are also not doing any type of interaction with the borrowers. So, the borrowers have no knowledge on non-performing assets which are in their interest. It is therefore suggested that the branches should arrange training cum awareness camps at different places in their area of operation once in a year and educate the borrowers on various issues. This will help both the borrowers and the banks in improving interaction with the borrowers and simultaneously improve the recovery atmosphere.

3. Helping Borrowers in Difficulties:

Some borrowers are not capable of paying bank dues due to their personal problems but that should be communicated to banks. If they will communicate then the dealing officer should prepare a list of overdue accounts and find the reason behind the same with the manager. After the discussion, only those accounts where there is no alternative available, that should be classified as NPAs.

4. Write Off of Loans:

Write off of Loans is one of the ways of reducing NPAs. However, it is necessary to ensure that before any account is written off, all the efforts for recovery of loan have failed and there is no possibility of recovery in the account in normal course of time.

5. Government Programmers:

There are some government sponsored programmers, such as SGSY, PMRY, SJSRY etc, which are implemented for the benefit of rural or urban poor, is not good at all because the recovery under these programmers was very poor. So government must ensure that the borrowers repay all the dues in due time.

6. Willful Defaulter:

Sometimes borrowers are declaring themselves as willful defaulters because they are experiencing that some borrowers are not paying and government let them go free. That induces other borrowers to follow the same path. This increases the volume of NPA. Therefore, government should take strong steps towards defaulters.

CONCLUSION

The Non-Performing Assets have always created a big problem for the banks in India. It is not only the problem for banks but also for the economy too. The money locked up in NPAs has a direct impact on profitability of the bank as Indian banks are highly dependent on income from interest on funds lent. This study shows that extent of NPA is comparatively very high in public sectors banks. Although various steps have been taken by government to reduce the NPAs but still a lot needs to be done to curb this problem. The NPAs level of our banks is still high as compared to the foreign banks. Though it is not at all possible to have zero NPAs, the bank management should speed up the recovery process. The problem of recovery is not with small borrowers but with large borrowers and a strict policy should be followed for dealing this problem. The government should also make more provisions for faster settlement of pending cases and also it should reduce the mandatory lending to priority sector as this is the major problem creating area. So the problem of NPA needs lots of serious efforts otherwise NPAs will be killing the profitability of banks which is not good for the growing Indian economy at all.

The financial institutions should develop new strategies to improve the recovery of loan. Non-performing assets (NPAs) affect the performance of financial institutions both financially as well as psychologically. The non-performing assets have become a major cause of concern. Absorbing the credit management skills has become all the more important for improving the bottom-line of the banking sector. The current NPAs status continues to disturb Indian banking Sector. Several experiments have been tried to reduce NPAs but nothing has hit the mark in tackling NPAs. The Indian banking sector face a serious problem of NPAs. A high level of NPAs suggests high probability of a large number of credit defaults that affect the profitability and liquidity of banks. Most of the problem related to NPA is faced by public sector banks. To improve the efficiency and profitability, the NPAs have to be scheduled. Strict measures are needed to be taken up to combat these NPAs crises. It is highly impossible to have zero percentage NPAs.

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